

CBT TO REDUCE CRIME

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RECOMMENDED

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GHD – CBT to Reduce Crime

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Note to readers: Our research is mainly aimed at AIM decision-makers and participants in our programs and is geared toward finding the best ideas for incubation. Given our commitment to focusing on recommended ideas, reports on those not recommended for incubation can often be less polished.

For questions about the content of this research, please contact James at james@charityentrepreneurship.com. For questions about the research process, please contact Morgan Fairless at morgan@charityentrepreneurship.com.

We are also grateful to the experts who took the time to offer their thoughts on this research. We would like to specifically acknowledge the contribution of Joel McGuire, who provided valuable insights and referred us to helpful resources and analysis. We also thank the team members at AIM, especially Samantha and Ben, who helped with the report.

Executive Summary

Crime has substantial costs to society at the individual, community, and national levels. Homicide, rape, assault, theft, burglaries are just a few examples of crime that has very real and obvious negative consequences. There are also crimes against businesses, like robberies, cargo theft, and cybercrime.

Interpersonal violence, for example, is a leading cause of death and disability among young people worldwide. Each year, over 176,000 homicides occur among youth aged 15-29, making up 37% of all homicides worldwide. Although less than 1% of the world die due to interpersonal violence, homicide is the third leading cause of death for this age group, with most victims being male ([WHO, 2023](#)).

Non-lethal violence also causes substantial disability. Sexual violence affects a significant proportion of youth – 1 in 8 young people report sexual abuse. Physical assaults can leave the victim with serious injuries, like paralysis and chronic pain from gunshot wounds. Survivors of non-lethal violence often face mental health challenges that afflict them for a long time.

The negative externalities of crime are also numerous. Aside from the direct harm to victims, crime has many negative externalities. These indirect consequences have the potential to be even more costly than the direct harms of crime. Examples include:

- Career and productivity loss for the criminals who are caught and incarcerated,
- Households and businesses need to invest in protective measures,
- Businesses decrease their investments and suffer productivity losses,
- Governments redirect resources to address crime-related issues, including prevention and persecution,
- Indirect subject-wellbeing effects for family members of victims and individuals living in high crime areas,
- People altering their behavior to avoid (or engage) in criminal activities,
- Reduced productivity for victims of crime while lost time at work,
- Loss of tourism and economic activity.

The prevalence of crime and interpersonal violence varies significantly across regions and countries, and the problem is especially bad in Latin America. As indicated by a [World Bank report](#), 8 out of 10 of the world's most violent countries and 42 of the world's 50 most violent cities are located in Latin America and the Caribbean. The region had a homicide rate of 24 per 100,000 population in 2015, which is four times the global average. The total economic cost of crime is estimated to be 3.55% of the region's GDP.

Criminals also vary by demographics, with men being predominant perpetrators of crime. A 2013 global study on homicide by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime revealed that males comprised approximately 95% of all convicted homicide perpetrators worldwide.

There is moderately strong evidence that cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) could reduce violence and criminality in high-risk young men. CBT is a form of psychological therapy that helps individuals recognize and modify distorted thoughts and beliefs, develop healthier coping mechanisms, and practice new behaviors through structured activities and exercises. Based on related systematic reviews and RCTs, our best guess is that CBT could reduce a participant's criminal behavior by around 30-50% (before adjusting for internal and external validity). There is evidence that these effects could last more than ten years, reducing a high number of crimes throughout that time. Based on this evidence, the intervention was recommended by Innovation for Poverty Action (IPA) as one of their "Best Bets" in emerging opportunities for impact at scale.

This report evaluates the promise of a charity providing a similar program in Latin America, given its leading rates of violence.

Our geographic assessment identifies South Africa¹, Brazil, Venezuela, Jamaica, and Honduras as particularly good target countries. These countries have high crime rates, leading to a significant DALY burden due to interpersonal violence. However, charities should gain local contextual information about crime in those countries before committing to a country of operation. In particular, we think the intervention would work best in cities where crime is predominantly disorganized (as opposed to crime organized by gangs and cartels), and we expect significant city-to-city variation for this.

The modeled cost-effectiveness of this charity is extremely high. With the direct effects, modeled for reducing homicide, rape, assaults, robbery, theft, car theft, and burglaries, and indirect effects of policing and judiciary system cost, we estimate that a charity providing CBT to high-risk youths in Brazil would avert a DALY-equivalent for every ~\$26, which is equivalent to ~38 DALYs per \$1000 spent. Additionally, we modeled the mental health effects on household members, which could generate a [WELLBY](#) for every \$119 spent or 8.4 WELLBYs for every \$1000.²

¹ South Africa is a promising target country, but we think NEPI, one of the existing organizations scaling this intervention in Africa, is likely to reach South Africa after they expand to Nigeria and Sierra Leone.

² Although highly speculative, we also modeled the benefits of averting business losses by reducing cargo theft and financial institution robberies. These effects add additional impact with a benefit-cost ratio of ~24:1.

Experts are generally in favor of this intervention. They cite the high cost of crime and neglectedness as strong arguments for this nonprofit idea. Some experts emphasized the benefits of avoiding organized criminals for effectiveness and safety reasons.

We have some uncertainties remaining. We have some doubts about the charity's ability to recruit and target high-crime youths. We also have less information about the specific effect sizes for reducing sexual violence as opposed to general crime. We have uncertainties around modeling the externalities, including how reduced crime affects investment and economic growth. We also have uncertainties around the displacement effects of crime and how much crime would be taken up by non-participants.

We have moderately strong concerns about the intervention's safety, especially for the facilitator staff and, to a lesser extent, the founders. However, a security risk expert has laid out mitigation strategies that are reasonably straightforward to implement. Other concerns include feedback loops, given the reliability of self-reported crime reductions.

Overall, we think this idea is worth recommending for entrepreneurs to launch. We believe the intervention has the potential to be highly cost-effective. We are excited by the substantial positive externalities of crime reduction that we did not model, including the spillover effects on the participants' peers. As a result, we think that the cost-effectiveness has considerable uncaptured upsides. While this intervention has uncertainty and challenges, we believe strong founders will be able to overcome these.

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Glossary

Acronym	Stands for
AIM	Ambitious Impact
BAM	Becoming a Man
CBT	Cognitive Behavioral Therapy
CEA	Cost-effectiveness analysis
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
DALY	Disability-adjusted life year
IPA	Innovations for Poverty Action
GBD	Global Burden of Disease
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GBP	Great British pound
HIC	High-income country
LAC	Latin America and the Caribbean
LMIC	Low-middle income country
M&E	Measurement and Evaluation
NEPI	Network for Empowerment and Progressive Initiative
OR	Odds ratio
RCT	Randomised controlled trials
READI	Rapid Employment and Development Initiative
SD	Standard Deviation
STYL	Sustainable Transformation of Youth in Liberia
TOC	Theory of Change
UK	United Kingdom
U.S.	United States
WELLBY	Well-being year
WHO	World Health Organization

1 Introduction

This report evaluates the idea of a new charity working on providing CBT to reduce crime and its promise for the Charity Entrepreneurship Incubation Program.

This report has been produced by Ambitious Impact (AIM). AIM's mission is to create more effective charities by connecting talented individuals with high-impact intervention opportunities. We achieve this goal through an extensive research process and our Charity Entrepreneurship Incubation Program.

This process began by sourcing hundreds of ideas for potential new charities from members of our wider network, then gradually narrowing them down and examining them in increasing depth. We use various decision tools to assess how promising interventions would be for future charity entrepreneurs, such as group consensus decision-making, weighted factor models, cost-effectiveness analyses, quality of evidence assessments, case study analyses, and expert interviews.

This process is exploratory and rigorous but not comprehensive—we did not research all ideas in depth. As such, our decision not to pursue a charity idea to the point of writing a full report does not reflect a view that the concept is not good.

2 Background

Crime as a cause area

Crime generates substantial costs to society at individual, community, and national levels. Homicide, rape, assault, theft, burglaries are just a few examples of crime that has very real and obvious negative consequences. There are also crimes against businesses, like robberies, cargo theft, and cybercrime. This report focuses on the types of crime committed most often by high-risk youths.

Interpersonal violence, for example, is a leading cause of death and disability among young people worldwide. Each year, over 176,000 homicides occur among youth aged 15-29, making up 37% of all homicides worldwide. Although less than 1% of the world die due to interpersonal violence, homicide is the third leading cause of death for this age group, with most victims being male ([WHO, 2023](#)).

The problem of crime extends beyond homicides and lives lost. For each young person killed, many more sustain injuries requiring hospital treatment. When it is not fatal, youth violence has a severe, often lifelong, impact on a person's physical, psychological, and social functioning. Some victims develop chronic pain or even paralysis from gunshot wounds ([Mercy et al., 2017](#)).

Sexual violence also affects a significant proportion of youth. For example, 1 in 8 young people have reported past sexual abuse, leading to psychological distress and long-term health effects ([WHO, 2023](#)).

Aside from the direct harm to victims, the negative externalities of crime can be significant. These indirect consequences can potentially be even more costly than the direct harms of crime ([Heeks et al., 2018](#); see Expert Interviews). Examples include:

- Career and productivity loss for the criminals who get caught and incarcerated.
- Loss of tourism and economic activity,
- Indirect subjective wellbeing effects for individuals living in high-crime areas,
- Households and businesses invest in protective measures,
- Companies lower their investment levels and suffer productivity losses,
- Governments redirect resources to address crime-related issues,
- Reduced productivity for victims of crime while lost time at work.
- People alter their behavior to avoid (or engage) in criminal activities.³

³ According to Gallup surveys provided by the polling firm, 61% of Chileans, 56% of Colombians, 52% of Mexicans, 51% of Brazilians and 49% of Argentines say they don't feel safe walking alone at night in their neighborhoods ([Oppenheimer 2023](#)).

Crime is particularly salient to people from a psychological perspective. For example, 63% of Americans describe the crime problem in the U.S. as either extremely or very serious ([Jones, 2023](#)). In Chile, half of the population considers crime the country's most important issue ([Oppenheimer, 2023](#)). Over two in five people (43%) in Latin America and the Caribbean consider crime and violence to be the biggest threat to their safety. Additionally, more than one-third (37%) would permanently relocate to another country if they could ([Lloyd's Register Foundation 2022](#)).

There are risk factors that are associated with high rates of crime in individuals. They include being young and male, poverty, lack of education, and limited economic opportunities. These high-risk youth are more likely to be involved in gangs, drug trafficking, and other forms of violent behavior, posing serious challenges to public safety and social stability ([Murray et al., 2013](#)).

A 2013 global study on homicide by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime revealed that males comprised approximately 95% of all convicted homicide perpetrators worldwide ([UNODC 2013](#)).

The prevalence of crime and interpersonal violence varies significantly across regions and countries. As indicated by a World Bank report ([2018](#)), 8 out of 10 of the world's most violent countries and 42 of the world's 50 most violent cities were situated in Latin America and the Caribbean.

Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) have an especially big crime problem. Despite tremendous progress in socioeconomic areas in the last decade, including a 4% annual growth rate and milestones such as halving the proportion of people living on less than US\$1.25 a day, crime in the region has increased ([Jaitman, 2017](#)).

With a homicide rate reaching 24 homicides per 100,000 population in 2015, the region accounts for 33 percent of the world's homicides despite being home to only 9 percent of the world's population. Robberies are on the rise in the region, and 6 out of 10 of them are violent ([Jaitman, 2017](#)).

High crime rates are estimated to cost Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) US\$174 billion annually. This is due to higher security expenses, investment losses, and resource relocations, which cause productivity declines. On average, these high crime rates cost each country in the region about US\$300 per capita (adjusted for purchasing power parity), or approximately 3.55% of their GDP ([Goh & Law, 2023](#); [Jaitman, 2017](#)).

Programs that prevent crime, directly or indirectly, can create significant economic benefits by lowering the costs associated with crime for victims, communities, and the criminal justice system.

Strategies to reduce crime: Cognitive Behavioural Therapy

There are many different strategies to reduce crime. Two prevalent policy approaches—job creation and policing—aim to decrease crime and violence by either altering the incentives for young men or by penalizing them. Another strategy focuses on rehabilitating high-risk men through therapy and counseling, promoting "character skills" like self-control and a non-criminal self-image.

Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) is a psychological intervention that aims to change harmful thoughts and behaviors. It is based on the premise that altering dysfunctional thinking patterns can change emotions and behavior.

CBT works by helping individuals recognize and modify distorted thoughts and beliefs, develop healthier coping mechanisms, and practice new behaviors through structured activities and exercises. CBT is a well-evidenced intervention to treat a variety of mental health disorders ([Uphoff et al., 2020](#); [Shinohara et al., 2013](#)).

Emerging evidence suggests that CBT could also be a promising intervention that reduces violence and criminality ([Blattman et al., 2015](#); [Blattman et al., 2022](#)).

The NEPI STYL program

The Network for Empowerment and Progressive Initiative (NEPI) was established in 2004. They developed an innovative CBT program for youths called the Sustainable Transformation of Youth in Liberia (STYL) program in response to the 14-year civil war in Liberia, which conscripted thousands of youths as combatants.

The STYL program combines an 8-week program of group CBT and cash transfer to rehabilitate youths. They targeted "hard-core street youth"—men aged 18 to 35 who were often homeless, involved in drugs and crime, living in severe poverty, or engaged in violence and other risky behaviors. Around 40% of the participants had been members of armed groups during Liberia's civil wars ([Blattman et al., 2015](#)).

The therapy sessions combined lectures, group discussions, and practical exercises. These included role-playing in class, homework assignments to practice tasks, real-life situation exposures, and in-class reflections on these experiences.⁴ Similar to other CBT programs, the tasks started simple and became more challenging

⁴ The therapy also promoted nonviolent and noncriminal behavior by encouraging a change in the men's social identity. A key idea of STYL was that these men saw themselves as outcasts and did not adhere to mainstream societal standards. The therapy aimed to convince them that they could change their self-identity and how they were perceived by others. They walked the men through basic steps, such as changing their appearance, engaging in normal social interactions, and behaving more cooperatively. They discouraged drug use and association with bad peers. Therapy also required men to practice going to supermarkets, banks, and other "normal" places.

over time. Due to the lack of formally trained psychologists or counselors in Liberia, all sessions were conducted by NEPI-trained facilitators, many of whom had previously been involved in armed groups or criminal activities and were graduates of earlier NEPI rehabilitation programs. Participants met three times a week in groups of about 20 people for 3-4 hours each session. Facilitators sometimes visited participants in their homes or workplaces on non-meeting days for one-on-one guidance and support ([Blattman et al., 2015](#)).

The STYL program was surprisingly effective at reducing crime. An RCT conducted by IPA and researchers has shown that STYL reduces crime and violence by 20-50% and that this effect lasts at least ten years at the latest follow-up time (more details in the Evidence section). Based on this evidence, IPA recommended this intervention as a “best bet” in emerging opportunities for impact at scale ([Burke, 2023](#)).

This report evaluates the promise of a charity providing a similar program in Latin America.

3 Theories of change

3.3 Theory of change of this charity

The theory of change (ToC) is based on replicating the work of NEPI and its STYL program in geographically neglected areas. Due to the scope of the report, we have not considered other interventions that reduce crime. So, this ToC represents a potentially promising way to reduce crime, but it may not be the *most* cost-effective way.

NEPI and IPA researchers have suggested that they would be willing to provide guidance and advice for a potential new charity.

The ToC of the charity looks like the following:

Note: Pink boxes denote optional steps of the ToC

The following assumptions are behind each numbered step in the diagram. They are color-coded based on our level of confidence.

1. The training program we put together is effective, and the nonprofit can recruit facilitators (mostly ex-criminals) to conduct the training.
2. There is an appropriate venue and time for the trainers and youths.

3. Youths are willing to join the program and go through the program with high engagement and adherence.
4. CBT is effective at altering youth beliefs; Belief changes can activate behavior changes.
5. Altered beliefs directly improve the participant's personal well-being.
6. Participants reduce criminal behavior as a result of behavior changes; there are no displacement effects, and overall societal crime levels also drop.
7. Participants have more productive careers and have a lower chance of being incarcerated for crimes.
8. Reduced crime leads to less suffering for victims, reduces societal anxiety, and increases well-being in society.
9. More productive members of society lead to stronger economic growth and increased personal income and employment rates for participants. Participants also experience increased well-being from not being incarcerated.

Optional steps

10. The government, police, or justice system are willing to cooperate and refer at-risk youths to the program.
11. Cash transfers increase the participant's sense of empowerment and support.
12. The increased empowerment and support strengthen the CBT's effectiveness.

Recruitment

NEPI primarily recruits participants via two methods:

1. Outreach specialists ask members of the community who they think are the troublemakers of the community. They then approach those men to recruit them into the program.
2. They also run a survey in the community and collect information about an individual's criminal activity. They approach the high-risk individuals to recruit them into the study.

Note on cash transfers

We think the charity would be more cost-effective if it focused on CBT without cash transfers. In our conversation with the CEO of NEPI, he mentioned that cash+CBT

generates larger and more sustained effects in crime reduction. We are uncertain whether the increase in the cost of the intervention from including a cash transfer justifies this effect from a cost-effectiveness perspective. From our interpretation of the data in the 'Evidence' section, we believe the effect sizes are similar, especially for non-drug related crimes (which are the types of crime we are most excited to reduce due to lower displacement effects). For this reason, we lean towards recommending the charity move away from the cash transfer portion and focus on CBT. However, we are uncertain and believe the founders should run further experiments in the pilot and consult more experts on this decision.

If the cash transfer is included, we would still expect the charity to meet our cost-effectiveness bar.

4 Quality of evidence

4.1 Evidence that a charity can effect change in this space

Several charities have done similar work in using CBT principles to reduce crime.

- The best evidence we have for a charity being able to do this is based on the Liberia RCT implemented by NEPI. As we discovered from the expert interviews, NEPI has restarted its operations in 2022 after a 10-year pause⁵. So far, they seem to have similar success in user acquisition and completion rates. However, they have not yet completed the measurement and evaluation of the recent cohorts.
- Youth Guidance also successfully delivered a CBT program to economically disadvantaged youths in Chicago and saw the potential for crime reduction.
- Glasswing implemented an after-school group-based behavior program in El Salvador and decreased delinquent and violent behaviors.
- **The results of these interventions are explored in detail in Section 4.3.**

At the same time, there are indications that the intervention is not simple to implement.

- Experts have mentioned recruitment challenges and noted that the city of Bogota trialed the intervention with little success due to the rushed implementation.

There are analogous charities from the AIM network:

- Vida Plena was founded in 2022 to provide group CBT for victims of mental health disorders in Ecuador. As noted in their annual impact report, they've had some success so far. In their pilot, 434 participants had an average reduction of 6.6 in the PHQ-9 questionnaire. 68% of participants with moderate to severe depression clinically improved (≥ 5 points drop in PHQ-9) ([Vida Plena, 2024](#)).
- StrongMinds is a charity that Vida Plena was modeled after. Good evidence suggests it is one of the most cost-effective mental health charities ([McGuire, 2021](#)).

⁵ From our understanding, NEPI ran the original RCT as an experiment and did not intend to continue the program. When the 10-year results came in and demonstrated such a large impact, they decided to restart the program.

4.2 Evidence that CBT reduces crime

Overall, we think there is moderately strong evidence that CBT effectively reduces crime. This is supported by the vast literature on the effectiveness of CBT in changing beliefs and behaviors. Based on the wide variety of contexts the studies were based on, we have moderate confidence that the intervention would be externally valid in a new country that the charity would target.

However, we remain uncertain about:

- The effect on different categories of crime
- The factors that are most relevant to the external validity, such as employment rates or wealth inequality.

Direct evidence from the literature

This article by J-PAL ([J-PAL Policy Insight, 2024](#))⁶ summarises the evidence that CBT prevents crime and violence. The following is a table summary that extracts the headline results from those studies (Table 1).

⁶ We highly encourage readers to read this article.

Table 1: Summary of the studies we found that evaluate CBT on crime reduction.

Study	Description	Results	Take up and adherence
NEPI STYL program (Blattman et al., 2015)	999 agreed to participate and were randomly assigned to four groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● No intervention ● Unconditional cash transfer of \$200 ● CBT therapy ● CBT therapy and cash transfer Measured at one year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Drug dealing and theft were reduced by 40% in the therapy+cash group ● Men reported being less impulsive and less oriented towards immediate rewards. ● Changes were stronger and most sustained when therapy was coupled with cash 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 999 out of 1500 participated ● 93% follow up at the one-year mark. ● Nearly all those assigned to therapy attended at least a day, and two-thirds completed it. ● The higher-risk men were the most likely to finish.
NEPI STYLE program (Blattman et al., 2022, Blattman, Sheridan, et al., 2022)	10-year follow-up of the NEPI STYL program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overall, 338 fewer crimes were committed over a 10-year period. Drug selling: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Therapy: reduced by 16% compared to control(p=0.542) ● Therapy+ cash: decreased by 45% (p=0.092) Theft and robberies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Therapy Only: Decreased by 1.0 crimes per 2 weeks (54% decrease, p=0.027). ● Therapy+Cash: Decreased by 0.92 crimes per 2 weeks (49% decrease, p=0.050). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 833 out of 999 original participants, representing 93% of surviving members.

		<p>Disputes and Fights:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Therapy Only: Decreased by 0.14 standard deviations (p=0.073). • Therapy+Cash: Decreased by 0.13 standard deviations (p=0.051). <p>Weapons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Therapy Only: Decreased by 7.5 percentage points (57% decrease, p=0.024). • Therapy+Cash: Decreased by 4.4 percentage points (33% decrease, p=0.205). <p>Arrests:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Therapy Only: Decreased by 1.2 percentage points (15% decrease, p=0.610). • Therapy+Cash: Decreased by 2.9 percentage points (36% decrease, p=0.217). <p>Aggressive Behaviors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Therapy Only: Decreased by 0.060 standard deviations (p=0.301). • Therapy+Cash: Decreased by 0.062 standard deviations (p=0.316). <p>Intimate Partner Abuse:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Therapy Only: Almost no change (0.032 standard deviation increase, p=0.767). • Therapy+Cash: Decreased by 0.082 standard deviations (p=0.453). 	
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<p>Cochrane review (Armeliuss & Andreassen, 2007)</p>	<p>Twelve trials looked at whether CBT was effective at reducing recidivism in adolescents.</p> <p>Eight studies were conducted in the USA, two in Canada, and two in the UK</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pooled data significantly favored CBT over standard treatment, with an odds ratio of 0.69. • On average, recidivism is reduced by about 10%. • The long-term effects were not statistically significant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not reported
<p>(Heller et al., 2017)</p>	<p>Two RCTs were conducted in Chicago, and a program called Becoming a Man (BAM) was tested. It was developed by the nonprofit Youth Guidance for economically disadvantaged youths.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in the program reduced total arrests during the intervention by 28-35% and reduced violent crime arrests by 45-50%. • It also improved school engagement and, in follow-up data, increased graduation rates by 12-19% • However, the effects of arrests did not persist beyond the program period. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not reported
<p>(Heller et al., 2017)</p>	<p>One RCT from Cook County Juvenile Temporary Detention Center</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced Readmission rates to the facility by 21% within an 18-month time frame. • Reduced admission rate by 39% within a two-month time frame. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not reported
<p>(Arbour 2022)</p>	<p>A quasi-experimental evaluation of a behavior</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced the likelihood of recidivism by 18 percentage points 	

	program implemented in provincial jails in Quebec	(60%) one year following release, though the program did not appear to impact prison misconduct or the likelihood of being granted parole	
(Bhatt et al., 2024)	RCT of Rapid Employment and Development Initiative (READI) Chicago tested in a cohort of 2,456 men at high risk for gun violence whether CBT and 18-month job programs would reduce gun violence.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After 20 months, there was no statistically significant change in the combined index of three serious violence measures, the study's main outcome. • Shooting and homicide arrests decreased by 65% ($p = 0.13$ after adjusting for multiple testing) • In a pre-specified group of participants referred by outreach workers, the decline in arrests and victimizations of shootings and homicides was down 79% and 43%, respectively. This was statistically significant even after multiple testing adjustments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 55% of men who were offered the program started it, and 78% among outreach referrals. • 75% still participated at the 20-week mark.
(Egana-delSol and Dinarte 2019)	After-school behavioral therapy program by the NGO Glasswing for vulnerable public school	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced bad behavior reports from teachers • Decreased delinquent and violent behaviors reported by students, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The average matching rate of administrative data of enrolled children was 94% at baseline and 97% at follow-up.

	students aged 10-16 in El Salvador	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lowered school absenteeism (by 23%) • Improving students' grades. • Additionally, the program positively impacted the behavior and academic performance of students who didn't participate but were exposed to peers who attended the therapy sessions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 968 of 1,056 baseline enrolled children (92%) were surveyed at endline.
(Lipsey 2007)	Meta-analysis of 58 studies of CBT programs to reduce recidivism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recidivism rates reduced on average by 25%, and the most effective configurations of CBT produced a 50% decrease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attrition from outcome measurement is virtually zero in a majority of the studies but ranges over 30% in some of the remaining ones.

Analogous evidence on police violence

There is weak evidence that behavioral interventions reduce police use of nonlethal force and discretionary arrests.

- The Situational Decision-Making (or Sit-D) program trained Chicago Police Department officers to think more systematically in ambiguous, high-stress situations through four four-hour sessions ([Dube et al., 2023](#)). In addition to drawing on principles from CBT, the training incorporated lessons from a broader behavioral science literature, including the psychology of judgment and decision-making.
 - **Use of Force:** Reduced nonlethal force and discretionary arrests by 23%.
 - **Racial Disparities:** Arrests of Black civilians decreased by 11% without affecting arrest rates for other groups, indicating a reduction in racial disparities.
 - **Improved Deliberation:** Training enhanced officers' ability to consider multiple interpretations of situations and update their assessments as conditions changed, leading to less reliance on default assumptions.

Analogous evidence on CBT in general mental health disorders

CBT, in general, is considered one of the most well-evidenced interventions for mental health disorders. It has been demonstrated to be effective in treating:

- Anxiety ([Hunot et al., 2007](#))
- Depression ([Uphoff et al., 2020](#); [Hetrick et al., 2016](#)): Happier Lives Institute evaluates StrongMind's effectiveness on individual recipients as 1.92 SDs of improvement in depression ([McGuire, 2021](#)).
- Alcohol and drug use problems ([Magill et al., 2019](#))
- Marital issues ([Epstein & Zheng, 2017](#))
- Eating disorders ([Linardon et al., 2017](#)).
- And others.

Given this evidence, although the CBT program is specifically redesigned to reduce criminality in high-risk individuals, it may have the side-benefit of improving the participants mental health and well-being, which we do not model for in the CEA.

Theories of crime reduction at the population level

The above evidence suggests that CBT could potentially reduce crime among participants, but the overall effect on crime in society is uncertain. There are two factors that we have very little data on:

Displacement of crime: It could be possible that other individuals in the society increase their crime due to the participants decreasing their criminal activity. This could be the case if there are only a certain number of opportunities for crime and criminals have saturated those opportunities; thus, reducing crime in one person only creates more opportunities for others. For example, this would be the case for crimes where there is a market demand for the crime, such as drug selling and trading – the overall demand for drugs would not decrease, and other criminals would sell more drugs to offset the reduction in participants.

Spillover effect (also called social multipliers) of crime reduction: Each participant influences the culture of criminality in society, and other criminals may model their behavior based on their peers' improved behavior. In this way, reducing crime among individuals could have larger spillover effects on reducing crime in society.

We think it is more likely that the spillover effects are larger than the displacement effects, though we are highly uncertain. The following are what we found based on 1 hour of research:

- There seems to be evidence of spillover effects from the El Salvador study ([Egana-delSol & Dinarte, 2019](#)).
- New fathers tend to have reduced crime rates after the birth of their child. This effect is larger if the child is a boy compared to a girl. By looking at the reductions in crime for the peers of these new fathers, Dustmann and Landerso ([2018](#)) were able to estimate a spillover effect of crime reduction of 4X. This means a reduction of one conviction of the father leads to five fewer convictions for him and his peers ([Dustmann & Landersø, 2018](#)).
- A paper looking at how the death of a co-offender influences the criminal activities of other network members found a significant spillover effect that decays the further out the connection ([Lindquist et al., 2024](#)). For the connections one step from the death, there was a 47% decrease in offenses and a 40% decrease in conviction rates compared to the predeath mean. For the connections two steps away from the death, the reduction in offenses is 14.6%.

- A systematic review of hot spot policing found that there was a diffusion benefit of crime prevention benefits associated with the interventions ([Braga et al., 2019](#)).
 - Related: Mears and Bhati ([2006](#)) found that when local communities were deprived of resources, homicide rates would increase in proximate areas even though their resources were unaffected, suggesting spillover effects.
- Analysis of crime data estimated that social multiplier effects are around 1.7 at the county level, 2.8 at the state level, and 8.2 at the national level. They also found evidence of other forms of social multipliers for human capital ([Glaeser et al., 2003](#))
- Experts have noted that CBT is unlikely to reduce organized crime, but rather impulsive and disorganized crime. This includes some categories of violent crimes and the majority of petty crimes.

There is also evidence of the contrary:

- In the City of Bogota, randomly assigned doubling of policing in specific streets did not decrease overall crime, and data suggests that crime was displaced to neighboring streets, especially property crimes ([Blattman et al., 2021](#)).

4.3 Evidence on externalities/second-order effects/potential harm

Overall, we think there is moderate evidence that reducing crime has an array of indirect externalities. Some of these were modeled in the CEA, such as the well-being effects for the victim's peers. Without modeling these externalities, we would still expect that charity to be cost-effective on its own. We think it is plausible that the cumulative effects of these externalities be larger than the direct effects of crime reduction and that the charity should design strategies to measure some of these secondary outcomes.

Evidence that reducing crime increases societal subjective wellbeing

There is moderate/weak evidence that higher crime rates lead to lower collective subjective well-being in society or immediate peers of victims. These are based mostly on correlative studies.

- A meta-analysis of 12 studies on the association between fear of crime and subjective well-being, using data from 39 countries and 407,474 subjects, found a negative correlation ($r = -0.15$) between the two. Insofar as fear of crime is likely to be correlated with actual levels of crime, the higher the crime levels, the greater the effect on subjective well-being ([Alfaro-Beracoechea et al., 2018](#)).
- Sulemana (2015) looks at the correlational effect of crime victimization across ~17k recipients in 20 African countries.
 - They find a 0.08 effect on a 0 to 10 life-satisfaction scale equivalent to someone in the household being subjected to at least one theft in the last year.
 - Assuming a household of 4-5 people, this translates to 0.36 WELLBYs per crime.
- Responses from 18,000 individuals aged 18 and above were collected during the Health in Times of Transition (HITT) survey in 2010/11 in ex-Soviet Union countries; experiencing violence was associated with significantly lower happiness and life satisfaction ([Stickley et al., 2015](#)).
 - On average, being a victim of violence leads to a -0.23 and -0.47 effect in reported life satisfaction, measured by two different methodologies. The p-value was <0.001 .
- A nationwide survey in Germany conducted in 2010 found that fear of crime and victimization experiences lower respondents' life satisfaction ([Hanslmaier, 2013](#)).
 - "Comparing the life satisfaction of people who had been victims in the previous two years with non-victims shows that about 24 percent of the victims are among the most satisfied, whereas more than 35 percent of the non-victims belong to this group. The differences are significant at the $p < .01$ level ($\chi^2 = 9.76$). Point-biserial analyses reveal that life satisfaction is negatively related to fear of crime (-0.12 ; $t = -6.78$; $df = 3200$); the relationship between the crime rate and life satisfaction is less strong but also significant (-0.04 ; $t = -2.07$; $df = 3218$)"

Evidence that reducing crime increases capital investments and economic growth

From a quick search, we found little direct and empirical evidence that reducing crime leads to increased capital investments and economic growth.

- Vaguely related: A systematic review of 6 papers found that economic and financial crimes negatively impact economic growth in emerging and developing countries ([Saddiq & Abu Bakar, 2019](#)).
- There seems to be a lot of reference to the vicious cycle of underinvestment in communities and increased crime, leading to more underinvestment in communities ([Walter et al., 2024](#)). The evidence for the latter half of the chain is lacking.
- A study looking at crime and consumer behavior found that crime negatively affects the number of visits and consumers to an area. This is especially true for crime in public spaces, as opposed to crime that occurs in private residences. The study also found evidence that night visits are more sensitive than day visits ([Fe and Sanfelice, 2022](#)).
- Rozo ([2014](#)) estimates that when homicide rates increase by 10%, white- and blue-collar workers' consumption decreases by 2.8% and 6.3%, respectively. Violent crime also increases inequality, and aggregate production falls by 2.1% because firms reduce production.

There is weak evidence that crime affects human capital investments, such as education.

- Koppensteiner and Menezes ([2019](#)), using within-school and within-corridor estimates, found that violence near schools negatively affects school attendance and standardized test scores in math and Portuguese and increases dropout rates.

Evidence that crime and incarceration affect the employment and wages of criminals

There is empirical and theoretical evidence that incarceration reduces the short-term wages of criminal offenders.

- When imprisoned, criminals can no longer work and be productive in society and, therefore, suffer short-term productivity losses. However, they also become less employable and suffer productivity losses even after release from jail. Some experts have noted that this, alongside the cost to the state for incarcerating individuals, is potentially the largest cost of crime.
- Garin et al. (2023) examined tax filings and criminal justice records to demonstrate that a year-long sentence reduces cumulative 5-year earnings by 13%. Interestingly, long-term incomes stabilize to pre-incarceration levels. The

authors believe this is because those populations already had difficult circumstances before incarceration.

- Czafit and Köllő ([2015](#)) also found the impact of a prison term to be negative on wages.
- Gordon et al. ([2023](#)) found that first-time incarceration is associated with a 33%-50% drop in expected lifetime earnings and 6-10 fewer years of employment for men with a high school degree.

5 Expert views

Heidi McAnnally-Linz – Board of Directors at NEPI

NEPI has decided to reinstate the CBT program and scale up with a \$1.5 million grant awarded from the Fund for Innovation in Development (FID). NEPI originally ran the Liberia RCT in 2009 but did not scale the program. After the ten-year IPA follow-up study, they decided to reinstate the program and scale up. The grant is expected to arrive in 2025.

They have plans to scale to Nigeria to serve at-risk youths. They have just restarted work, and initial results seem as promising as the trial from 15 years ago. More results in the next 6-12 months will demonstrate the robustness of the intervention.

Despite the ambitious scaling plans of NEPI, significant gaps remain, and there could be space for another organization. However, a new organization should work closely with NEPI.

Heidi thinks the program will need philanthropic money to scale, while the NEPI team thinks the government would fund it. She expresses skepticism about the political tractability of getting government funding for such a program.

Heidi believes the best solutions come from the people closest to the problem. When she worked in IPA, she got to know Johnson and was sold by the team with Chris Blattman, a professor at the University of Chicago. Johnson is great but needs a co-founder to help out.

NEPI believes that the benefits of reducing crime are enormous. This includes the cost to productivity, from reducing investments in an area to changing a person from a less productive to a more productive one. Many studies don't seem to measure the cost of crime in LMICs, but studies exist for OECD countries.

This intervention seems to be one of the most cost-effective means of reducing crime.

There is uncertainty around targeting and recruitment. At-risk youths are hard to find and recruit, as it requires them to participate voluntarily. Schools are not significant touchpoints because they usually drop out by grade 6-7. If we target grade 5 students,

they would be too young to follow the program, and the intervention would have to be very different. Right now, the targeting work is more community-based.

Part of the purpose of the cash transfer is to demonstrate that the team stands behind the at-risk youths and provides them with an opportunity to change their life. A comparison was drawn between this and the graduation approach⁷.

Johnson Borh - CEO of NEPI

NEPI restarted in 2022, focusing primarily on the STYL (therapy+cash) program. They have run two rounds of the program once per year. However, they have not begun the follow-up measurements for the first round, so we have yet to see if the program is as effective as before.

NEPI continues to experiment with and trial incremental improvements to the program, including setting up a new M&E system and recruitment systems and testing booster sessions.

1. Recruitment used to be done through the community. J-PAL has helped develop a survey to analyze antisocial behavior so that NEPI can identify the highest-risk youths to target. Recruitment has never been a big challenge, and considering there is so much crime, there is a large demand from participants.
2. NEPI is trialing a new digital phone-based M&E system. However, it has been challenging, as participants may be busy and don't want to be on the phone, or there may be background noise or distractions.

It has not been difficult to recruit facilitators for the program. They tend to be former participants who have gone through it.

Johnson is excited about working in South America but is currently focused on testing external validity in other African nations first. He wouldn't be against another organization launching in South America if there were funds and resources available. The program is designed in English now, and materials would have to be adapted.

NEPI plans to scale via a franchising/technical assistance model. While NEPI is focusing on scaling in Liberia, they hope to scale to other countries via hands-on technical assistance to other organizations. From their scoping exercise, they have identified Nigeria and Sierra Leone as the next locations to test the program.

⁷ The graduation approach is a comprehensive strategy that combines social protection, livelihoods promotion, and financial inclusion to help the ultra-poor achieve sustainable livelihoods and escape extreme poverty.

In the long term, NEPI would like to receive government grants and multilateral agency funding.

Therapy+cash is more effective at reducing overall crime rates than therapy alone.

Although therapy alone had larger effects on theft and robberies specifically, overall crime rates were reduced the most in the therapy and cash cohort, which was why NEPI is focusing exclusively on this later program and no longer running test arms for therapy only. Their belief is that the cash transfer allows them to practice what they have learned from CBT.

The cash transfer has been adjusted upwards due to inflation. They now provide \$300 in cash instead of \$200.

IPA Research Team

Researchers for Innovations in Poverty Action (IPA) working on this topic are excited to support a new organization with the scaling of this intervention in high-potential cities in Latin America.

Some limited work is being done in Latin America. It is mostly state-led but also run by very small organizations like Sagaz and Glasswing International.

The nonprofit would have to deeply understand the nuances of the criminal context in different cities. The researchers highlighted that the intervention may be more effective against disorganized or impulsive crime than organized crime. Hence, it's more likely to work in places like Monrovia, Cali, and Bogota, where crime occurs at the individual or small fragmented group level. It likely wouldn't be as effective in Medellín or Rio.

Crime prevention efforts need to target high-risk populations, no matter which country or city. There are about 1000 young men in every 1 million who cause the most conflict, violence, and crime. The context usually determines whether this crime is organized or disorganized.

To reduce crime, we need three things: 1. To scale proven interventions 2. To develop cost-benefit analyses so we know how to fully capture the benefits of this work 3. To continue to experiment and test new interventions. IPA is well positioned to produce the evidence for 3, but AIM would be better suited for 1 and 2.

The implementation fidelity is highly important. There have been examples in the past with rushed implementation, like in Bogota, leading to facilitators not being properly trained or poorly selected.

Relatedly, one key path to failure is that the facilitators are not well-trained enough in CBT and begin to stray into other forms of psychotherapy (maybe because of previous training). This also presents a challenge to scaling. However, it may be easier in Latin America than in Africa since there are more existing social workers and CBT-trained therapists.

Scaling is probably best through implementation partners. It is quite important for the program to be run by local groups with established connections with these youths and knowledge of the space.

The key to recruiting and targeting participants is organization capacity. This includes outreach staff with the trust and connections with the target population. Identifying high-risk youths is likely easier than recruitment given strong community knowledge of who these people are.

Violence during CBT sessions is a very real risk. The organization needs to have a plan for dealing with this when it happens, including providing training for facilitators to handle such situations.

The inconsistent nature of funding sources has been a challenge. High-income countries tend to have robust funding budgets for crime prevention, but in low-income countries, governments may be more sporadic in supporting these interventions. Funding would likely have to come from a mix of government and philanthropic sources.

Funding agencies like USAID want to know what the long-term sustainable funding source is.

Former special constable in the UK

For four years, this expert has worked as a special constable in the UK, a volunteer police force. Most of the work involves foot patrols.

The expert thinks that CBT could be promising, but it depends on how exactly it's executed. They particularly like this idea of intervention because they disagree with popular sociology theories suggesting that offenders have no agency and are a product of their environment only. This intervention treats criminals as having high agency.

They emphasized the different categories of crime and how CBT may vary in effectiveness depending on their nature. For example, violent crime, organized crime (like dealing drugs), and shoplifting/mugging/robbery are categorically different.

The prevalent theory on violent crime offenders is that they have low executive control and a less adept prefrontal cortex, causing more impulsive behaviors. CBT may be able to interrupt this and shift the behavior.

Shoplifting, mugging, and robbery are more opportunistic in nature and reflect the offender's identifying lifestyle. Their identity relates to their worldview, values, and self-concept. They often believe they don't belong or fit in with society. If CBT can shift the offender's identity, then this could be promising. Many of these crimes are also premeditated and rely less on impulse, so CBT may be able to shift the behavior, given that there is more time for the individual to think through their actions.

Most violent crimes are gang-related in London. There are also strong pulls, such as community comradery and gang participation. Organized crime tends to be run as protection rackets. In London, this tends to be a misguided life path choice as gang members tend to quickly end up either in prison or as victims of violence. In high-crime LMICs, however, it could be the case that the gangs are sufficiently powerful and economic opportunities so poor that there are fewer viable alternatives for people. Thus, joining a gang may be rational in this situation. CBT may be less effective against this.

A small proportion of people commit the vast majority of crimes. It is important to target interventions for these people.

Some believe that crime rates have less to do with GDP per capita and more to do with income inequality.

Country comparisons are difficult because you can draw a lot of false inferences. Many governments have the incentive to downplay the true crime rates in statistics. It is slightly better when looking at data comparing within a country.

The indirect costs to society are expected to be even greater than the direct costs, such as personal injuries and economic losses. These indirect costs include the significant costs of policing, the judiciary process, and incarceration. The expert noted that this could cost £44,000 per prisoner in the UK, not including the trial cost.

Crime has an economic impact on businesses and spending. It makes it difficult for people to operate businesses. People are less likely to park cars in the area and shop there. However, the security industry will also lose sales if crime rates improve.

There is theory and evidence around sentencing interventions to reduce crime rates. Some evidence suggests that the likelihood of getting caught factors much more into offenders' decision-making than the severity of the crime. Shorter sentences are also associated with higher reoffending rates. There is a sense that with

longer sentences, the offender has been punished, and the debt to society has been repaid.

From a policing perspective, preventing crime is a constant war of attrition. It is believed that perfect policing would not be able to stop all crime, and the purpose of policing is to disrupt criminal activities and add friction.

Brechtje van den Bosch - Risk Management Expert

Brechtje offers a few strategies for mitigating risk to the founders and staff of the charity.

The charity should target high-risk individuals who are not involved in organized crime or gangs, which reduces the likelihood of conflicts with gang activities. The facilitators, being ex-offenders themselves, might face moderate risks of being targeted, but their respect from participants could mitigate this risk. However, the risk of violence or aggression during sessions is high, necessitating effective measures to manage and minimize these incidents.

To address the high likelihood of violence, it is crucial to implement recurring training sessions on de-escalation and conflict resolution for facilitators. This training should be factored into the cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) to ensure its inclusion in the program's budget. Additionally, a strict no-weapons policy should be enforced during sessions to reduce the risks associated with weapons. Facilitators should also receive crisis intervention training, and at least two trained professionals should be present at each session, with panic buttons available to enhance safety.

Health precautions are also important. Facilitators should be provided with vaccinations for diseases such as hepatitis, considering the health risks involved in working with high-risk individuals.

Regarding the local context, avoiding interference with gangs is essential to prevent becoming a target. It is important to thoroughly investigate the local environment to understand gang violence rates and adjust strategies accordingly. Facilitators' continuous feedback will be vital for making informed decisions about outreach and recruitment.

During outreach activities, safety measures such as traveling in pairs, maintaining communication, and blending into the local environment should be adopted.

Outreach personnel should avoid wearing expensive clothing when performing their duties. Using trained facilitators for outreach can help manage the risks of violence and ensure that the program's safety protocols are upheld.

If properly implemented, these measures can be simple to implement, but they should be considered in the costs of the intervention.

6 Geographic assessment

The geographic assessment was done in two stages. First, we looked at where existing organizations are working or have worked. This information was used as input in the formal geographic assessment to measure how much attention an issue is being paid. Second, we conducted a formal geographic assessment to find the top priority countries for starting a new nonprofit.

We consider this a rudimentary geographic assessment that provides a rough indication of the most promising countries. Because crime varies so much between cities, the charity would benefit from conducting a deeper urban analysis of crime in specific cities. The charity could analyze which high-crime cities are dominated by organized crime or disorganized crime.

6.1 Where existing organizations work

The main organization working on this intervention is NEPI. They operate in Liberia and plan to scale to Nigeria and Sierra Leone via franchising and technical assistance to other organizations. If the program is effective in Nigeria and Sierra Leone, they have ambitions to scale further.

There were some other organizations mentioned by the experts, but they were very small-scale and local. They include:

- [Glasswing](#) International works across Central America.
- SAGAS

6.2 Geographic assessment

In our [geographic assessment](#), we included indexes and data that provide proxies for the scale, neglectedness, and tractability of the intervention in different countries.

Scale

- **Interpersonal Violence DALY rate:** The rate of violence according to GBD
- **Population:** A proxy for how large the scale of each country would be
- **Homicide Rate:** A proxy for the crime rate in the country
- **Country Crime Index (NUMBEO):** A proxy for the crime rate in the country

- **The Global Organized Crime Index (GOCI):** A proxy for the crime rate in the country
- **No. of cities in top 20 crime index:** A proxy for the crime rate in the country, with a focus on crime in cities.

Neglectedness

- **Number of organizations working here**
- **GNI per capita (PPP)**
- **CrimeRate_ResilienceScore**

Tractability

- **Fragile States Index (2022)**
- **Corruption Perceptions Index (2021)**
- **WJP Rule of Law Index (2022)**
- **Freedom in the World (2022)**

Together, these indexes form a weighted average score of the promisingness of the target countries. The top 10 most promising countries are as follows:

Country	Weighted average
South Africa	1.633
Brazil	1.451
Venezuela	1.167
Jamaica	0.835
Honduras	0.831
Trinidad and Tobago	0.746
United States of America	0.734
El Salvador ⁸	0.719
Mexico	0.718
Lesotho	0.670

⁸ We have reason to believe that the data for El Salvador is outdated and that crime rates have significantly dropped in the last two years. The President, Nayib Bukele, has [locked up 76,000 people, causing the murder rate to fall from 53 per 100,000 in 2018 to 2.4 per 100,000 last year.](#)

7 Cost-effectiveness analysis

Our [Cost-effectiveness analysis \(CEA\)](#) models for a charity to implement the **Therapy-only part of the STYL program in Brazil**. We modeled the charity to reach 0.25% of the criminals, representing ~5,300 participants per year at scale.

We modeled the effects of a charity that reaches ~10k people per year at scale and the direct health effects of reducing homicides, assaults, sexual violence, and the equivalent income losses of robberies, car thefts, and burglary.

The charity is modeled to be extremely cost-effective (Table 2). We expect the charity to avert a DALY equivalent for ~\$26, or ~38 DALYs for every \$1000 spent. In addition, we expect the charity to gain a WELLBY for \$119, or 8.4 WELLBYs for every \$1000 spent.

In addition, we think the charity would avert economic damages to businesses and financial institutions of ~\$5300 per person reached. This is equivalent to a benefit-cost ratio of ~24:1, just considering business benefits.

Table 2: Summary of headline cost-effectiveness results

Total cost (per successful charity)	\$12,440,436
Total DALYs adjusted for targeting and for indirect effects (DALYs)	471,797
\$/DALY	\$26.37
DALY/\$1000	37.92
\$/WELLBY (additional)	\$119
WELLBY/\$1000 (additional)	8.40
\$ saved for businesses With good targeting + indirect costs	\$28,017,968
BCR	23.59

With so many effects and considerations, this is a very complex CEA. This is a breakdown of what is included in the CEA, but we recommend the reader go through the CEA for the details.

7.1 Effects

We estimated the crime reduction effect by categorizing the studies listed in Table 1 into two types of crime:

- Violent
- General crime

For each type, we generated a weighted average of the expected effects based on the studies that report that type of crime. We discounted these effect sizes based on external and internal validity.

The first category of benefits was the averted harm to individuals (the victims of crimes). We took the average crime rate for each subcategory of crime, divided by the percentage of the population who are perpetrators, to get the average number of crimes committed against individuals per offender for:

- Homicides
- Rape
- Assault
- Robbery and Mugging
- Car Theft
- Burglary

Based on the reductions stratified by violent vs. non-violent effect sizes, we could then calculate the DALY benefit of reducing Homicide, rape, and assault as well as the income benefit of reducing robbery, car theft, and burglary, which could be converted to DALY-equivalents.

The second category of benefits was the averted harm to businesses. Similar to the above, calculated the average number of crimes committed per offender for:

- Cargo theft
- Robberies of financial institutions

The losses to businesses are difficult to translate into an impact on individuals' incomes. We separated this outcome and reported it as a benefit-to-cost ratio (BCR) of averting these losses.

The third category of effects we modeled was the well-being gains of the family members of victims. Based on two studies ([Stickley et al., 2015](#); [Sulemana 2015](#)), we calculated the average WELLBY gained per crime averted and added up the expected number of crimes we would avert to calculate the total WELLBYs that would be gained from the intervention.

Finally, we made adjustments based on the following:

- Targeting bonus: increasing the number of crimes per offender because we expect the people we target to commit more crimes than the average criminal.

- Indirect effects: The additional benefits associated with reduced prevention and governmental and judicial processing costs.
- The number of years the impact lasts: Here, we model the reductions to last ten years and end immediately after.

We also made standard discounts for the following:

- Probability of success
- Displacement effects
- Time discounts

7.2 Costs

Fixed costs: At scale, we modeled the charity as having about four full-time staff members, with a fixed cost of \$280,000.

Variable costs: The variable costs per participant are calculated by taking a weighted average of two methods:

- Method 1 (30%): from the quoted costs of the NEPI Liberia study, adjusted upwards for inflation and minus the cash transfer portion.
- Method 2 (70%): bottom-up calculation by multiplying the following:
 - Program manager salary
 - Program manager-to-participant ratio
 - Facilitator salary
 - Facilitator to facilitator-participant ratio

7.3 Reasons for errors

There are many reasons why the CEA could overestimate or underestimate the actual cost-effectiveness of the intervention. We list these in Table 3

Table 3: Reasons that CEA could be overestimated or underestimated

Reasons this intervention could be more cost-effective than modeled, all else equal.	Reasons this intervention could be less cost-effective than modeled, all else equal.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overall, we think the numbers are quite conservative. For example, the indirect 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Although the studies measure aggressive behavior, weapons carrying, and frequency of

Reasons this intervention could be more cost-effective than modeled, all else equal.

- cost of crime and targeting adjustments could be larger.
- Other crimes are not modeled, like vandalism or drug crimes.
 - Social multipliers (spillover effects were not modeled)
 - Effects could last beyond the ten years that we modeled for.
 - We did not model additional externalities, such as productivity losses for victims due to lost time at work or productivity losses to offenders due to incarceration.
 - The WELLBY effect was only modeled to benefit the victims' household members. Friends and larger members of society would probably see improvements in well-being with reductions in crime.

Reasons this intervention could be less cost-effective than modeled, all else equal.

- fights, they did not directly measure the homicide rates of participants. This could mean we have significantly overestimated the homicide reduction effects of the intervention.
- We assumed the facilitation space to be free.
 - We assumed the program managers would do the outreach and not require additional outreach staff.
 - We didn't include costing of conflict mediation training.
 - Some effect sizes modeled may not be externally valid; for example, we have little information about the direct reductions in rape (as opposed to violent crime) or cargo thefts and robberies.
 - We assume that any income the offender gains from crime, i.e. the economic rewards of their theft and robberies to be zero.

8 Implementation

8.1 What does working on this idea look like?

At a high level, this idea would be similar to working on delivery group CBT, like Vida Plena or StrongMinds. This involves training facilitators to run the program, managing outreach workers to recruit participants, and organizing the logistics of the group therapy sessions.

Depending on the measurement and evaluation methods, the team may need to spend considerable time tracking down participants for follow-up surveying.

The team would likely collaborate closely with NEPI, and if it decides to attach a cash transfer to the intervention, it may collaborate with GiveDirectly.

8.2 Key factors

This section summarizes our concerns (or lack thereof) about different aspects of a new charity's implementation of this idea.

Table 3: Implementation concerns

Factor	How concerning is this?
Talent	Low-moderate concern
Access to information	Low-moderate concern
Access to relevant stakeholders	Low-moderate concern
Feedback loops	Moderate concern
Funding	Moderate concern
Neglectedness	Low Concern
Execution difficulty/Tractability	Moderate concern
Complexity of scaling	Moderate concern
Risk of harm	Moderate-high concern

Talent

We have some concerns about finding founders to start this charity. We think at least one of the founders could benefit from experience working with criminals or high-risk youths (Table 4).

NEPI may apply for the program in search of a cofounder, the profile of which is likely similar to any generalist AIM charity founder.

We are likely to support the launch of an additional Latin American organization. If targeting a Latin American country, it would benefit the founders to speak Spanish (or Portuguese if targeting a Brazilian city).

Table 4: Founder requirements and nice to haves

Must have	Preferable (offsets a 10% diff in incubatee strength)	Preferable, all else equal
	Experience with providing CBT Experience working with criminals and convicts	If we target South America, then Spanish-speaking would be an advantage. Degrees in psychology or conflict studies Ex-criminal/ convict

Access

Information

We have a low-moderate concern about the charity's access to information. NEPI and IPA researchers have demonstrated a willingness to support and collaborate with a new charity. However, this area is relatively understudied compared to many other global health and development interventions.

Relevant stakeholders

We have low-moderate concerns about access to stakeholders, in particular the participants. From the perspective of connecting with other relevant organizations and expertise, we are not too concerned, as NEPI and Chris Blattman's team have demonstrated a level of support. Our main concern is whether the charity could reach and target the individuals at the highest risk of committing crimes. In the studies and

from expert interviews, NEPI has not found it difficult, but we have some doubts remaining.

Feedback loops

We have moderate concerns about the intervention feedback loops. The studies have mostly relied on self-reports of criminality, and although the researchers have taken steps to limit biases, including following participants to observe their criminal behavior directly, self-reports are still not the most reliable.

The charity could plausibly devise creative ways to measure the impact on crime, including surveying family members and friends of participants or collaborating with local law enforcement to determine rates or arrests.

If the charity can operate at a large enough scale, it may be powerful enough to generate effects observable at the population level. This could be easier to measure via cluster RCTs.

Some of the secondary effects would be complicated but useful to measure. These include the well-being of community members and economic benefits.

Funding

Funding from funders in the AIM network

We have some concerns about funding from the AIM network. Crime is not a well-established cause area among the funders in our network and may be viewed as out of scope for some. However, we believe funders in the network are open to funding such interventions if the cost-effectiveness looks promising.

Broader funding sources

We also have concerns and uncertainties around the funding appetite for such an intervention. We know NEPI recently received a large \$1.5 million grant to scale the intervention, which gives us some optimism. However, we also know that they have had large short-term funding gaps.

Some experts have mentioned the inconsistency of funding in this space, especially when relying on government funding for crime reduction programs.

Neglectedness

We are not concerned about neglectedness. NEPI is the only other organization doing work in the area, and they are only just beginning to consider scaling beyond Liberia to Nigeria and Sierra Leone. An additional organization in South America could be quite complementary.

Tractability

We have moderate concerns about the intervention's tractability. As mentioned, we are uncertain whether the charity could effectively reach and target the individuals at the highest risk of committing crimes. Although NEPI has not found it difficult, we still have some doubts.

Complexity of scaling

We have some concerns about scaling the intervention. As discussed, we have some concerns about the tractability of recruiting and targeting high-risk youths; doing this at scale presents another challenge.

Risk of harm

By the nature of the intervention, the charity would interact with criminals or people at high risk of committing violence or crime. We don't expect the founders to be directly in danger on a day-to-day basis, especially considering they would not be the direct facilitators of the CBT. However, there are increased security risks to consider.

Experts have mentioned the need to train facilitators to handle interpersonal conflict situations.

An expert also speculated that if provided to organized criminal leaders, the intervention could increase their effectiveness in committing crimes.

8.3 Remaining uncertainties

We have some doubts remaining about the charity's ability to recruit and target high-crime youths.

Large uncertainty remains around whether participants' reduced aggressive behaviors and fights translate to reduced homicides. Or whether reductions in crime in general translate to sexual violence.

We have large uncertainties around the externalities, including how reduced crime affects investment and economic growth.

Although we think the evidence base for the intervention is moderately strong, we have some uncertainties about the nuances regarding external valid contexts. The Liberia RCT was done mainly in a post-conflict setting, and while there are other studies spanning a wide range of geographic locations, we are still a bit uncertain about other contextual factors that may affect the effect size. For example, how do unemployment rates or inequality in the area affect the effectiveness of CBT?

9 Conclusion

Overall, we think this idea is worth recommending for entrepreneurs to launch. We believe the intervention has the potential to be highly cost-effective. We are excited by the substantial positive externalities of crime reduction that we did not model, including the spillover effects on the participants' peers. As a result, we think that the cost-effectiveness has considerable uncaptured upsides. While this intervention has uncertainty and challenges, we believe strong founders will be able to overcome these.

References

- Alfaro-Beracoechea, L., Puente, A., da Costa, S., Ruvalcaba, N., & Páez, D. (2018). Effects of fear of crime on subjective well-being: A meta-analytic review. *The European Journal of Psychology Applied to Legal Context*, 10(2), 089–096.
- Arbour, W. (2022). *Can Recidivism Be Prevented From Behind Bars? Evidence From a Behavioral Program*.
https://github.com/williamarbour/JMP/blob/main/JMP_WilliamArbour_recent.pdf
- Armeliu, B.-A., & Andreassen, T. H. (2007). Cognitive-behavioral treatment for antisocial behavior in youth in residential treatment. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 4, CD005650.
- Bhatt, M. P., Heller, S. B., Kapustin, M., Bertrand, M., & Blattman, C. (2024). Predicting and preventing gun violence: An experimental evaluation of READI Chicago. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 139(1), 1–56.
- Blattman, C., Green, D. P., Ortega, D., & Tobón, S. (2021). Place-based interventions at scale: The direct and spillover effects of policing and city services on crime. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 19(4), 2022–2051.
- Blattman, C., Jamison, J., & Sheridan, M. (2015). Reducing crime and violence: Experimental evidence on adult noncognitive investments in Liberia. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2594868>
- Blattman, C., Jamison, J., Sheridan, M., & Chaskel, S. (2022). *Cognitive Behavioral Therapy as a Cost-Effective Tool for Sustained Violence Reduction*. IPA.
<https://poverty-action.org/sites/default/files/2023-01/CBT-as-a-Cost-Effective-Tool-for-Sustained-Violence-Reduction-June-2022.pdf>
- Blattman, C., Sheridan, M. A., Ph. ., Jamison, J. C., & Chaskel, S. (2022). Cognitive behavior therapy reduces crime and violence over 10 years: Experimental evidence. In *SocArXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/q85ux>

- Braga, A. A., Turchan, B., Papachristos, A. V., & Hureau, D. M. (2019). Hot spots policing of small geographic areas effects on crime. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 15(3), e1046.
- Burke, L. (2023). *Best Bets: Emerging Opportunities for Impact at Scale*. IPA.
<https://poverty-action.org/sites/default/files/2023-11/IPA-Best-Bets-Report-Updated.pdf>
- Czafit, B., & Köllő, J. (2015). Employment and wages before and after incarceration – evidence from Hungary. *IZA Journal of European Labor Studies*, 4(1), 1–21.
- Dube, O., MacArthur, S. J., & Shah, A. K. (2023). A cognitive view of policing. *Working Paper Series (National Bureau of Economic Research)*.
https://www.nber.org/system/files/working_papers/w31651/w31651.pdf
- Dustmann, C., & Landersø, R. (2018). Child's Gender, Young Fathers' Crime, and Spillover Effects in Criminal Behavior. *Centre for Research and Analysis of Migration Discussion Paper Series*, 129(12), 3261–3301.
- Egana-delSol, P., & Dinarte, L. (2019). *Preventing Violence in the Most Violent Contexts: Behavioral and Neurophysiological Evidence*. World Bank.
<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/entities/publication/3dc59721-8ff3-54d8-bad2-a1ed886c6f2e>
- Epstein, N. B., & Zheng, L. (2017). Cognitive-behavioral couple therapy. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 13, 142–147.
- Fe, H., & Sanfelice, V. (2022). How bad is crime for business? Evidence from consumer behavior. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 129(103448), 103448.
- Garin, A., Koustas, D., McPherson, C., Norris, S., Pecenco, M., Rose, E. K., Shem-Tov, Y., & Weaver, J. (2023, August 9). *The Impact of Incarceration on Employment, Earnings, and Tax Filing*. BFI; Becker Friedman Institute for Economics at UChicago.

<https://bfi.uchicago.edu/insight/research-summary/the-impact-of-incarceration-on-employment-earnings-and-tax-filing/>

- Glaeser, E. L., Sacerdote, B. I., & Scheinkman, J. A. (2003). The social multiplier. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 1(2-3), 345–353.
- Goh, L. T., & Law, S. H. (2023). The crime rate of five Latin American countries: Does income inequality matter? *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 86, 745–763.
- Gordon, G., Jones, J. B., Neelakantan, U., & Athreya, K. (2023). Incarceration, employment, and earnings: Dynamics and differences. *Review of Economic Dynamics*, 51, 677–697.
- Hanslmaier, M. (2013). Crime, fear and subjective well-being: How victimization and street crime affect fear and life satisfaction. *European Journal of Criminology*, 10(5), 515–533.
- Heeks, M., Reed, S., Tafhiri, M., & Prince, S. (2018). *The economic and social costs of crime second edition*. UK GOV.
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-economic-and-social-costs-of-crime>
- Heller, S. B., Shah, A. K., Guryan, J., Ludwig, J., Mullainathan, S., & Pollack, H. A. (2017). Thinking, fast and slow? Some field experiments to reduce crime and dropout in Chicago. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 132(1), 1–54.
- Hetrick, S. E., Cox, G. R., Witt, K. G., Bir, J. J., & Merry, S. N. (2016). Cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), third-wave CBT and interpersonal therapy (IPT) based interventions for preventing depression in children and adolescents. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 2016(8), CD003380.
- Hunot, V., Churchill, R., Silva de Lima, M., & Teixeira, V. (2007). Psychological therapies for generalised anxiety disorder. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 1,

CD001848.

Jaitman, L. (2017). *The Costs of Crime and Violence: New Evidence and Insights in Latin America and the Caribbean*. Inter-American Development Bank.

<https://publications.iadb.org/en/publications/english/viewer/The-Costs-of-Crime-and-Violence-New-Evidence-and-Insights-in-Latin-America-and-the-Caribbean.pdf>

Jones, J. M. (2023, November 16). *More Americans See U.S. Crime Problem as Serious*. Gallup.

<https://news.gallup.com/poll/544442/americans-crime-problem-serious.aspx>

J-PAL Policy Insight. (2024). *Preventing crime and violence with behavior change techniques*. The Abdul Latif Jameel Poverty Action Lab (J-PAL).

<https://www.povertyactionlab.org/policy-insight/preventing-crime-and-violence-behavior-change-techniques>

Koppensteiner, M. F., & Menezes, L. (2019). *Violence and Human Capital Investments*.

IZA – Institute of Labor Economics. <https://docs.iza.org/dp12240.pdf>

Linardon, J., Wade, T. D., de la Piedad Garcia, X., & Brennan, L. (2017). The efficacy of cognitive-behavioral therapy for eating disorders: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, 85*(11), 1080–1094.

Lindquist, M. J., Patacchini, E., Vlassopoulos, M., & Zenou, Y. (2024). Spillover in Criminal Networks: Evidence from Co-offender Deaths. *IZA Institute of Labor Economics Discussion Paper*. <https://docs.iza.org/dp17113.pdf>

Lipsey, M. (2007). *Effects of cognitive-behavioral programs for criminal offenders* (Vol. 3, pp. 1–27). The Campbell Collaboration. <https://doi.org/10.4073/csr.2007.6>

Lloyd's Register Foundation. (2022). *Latin Americans fear crime and violence more than anyone globally*. Lloyd's Register Foundation.

<https://www.lrfoundation.org.uk/en/news/latin-america-fear-violence/>

- Magill, M., Ray, L., Kiluk, B., Hoadley, A., Bernstein, M., Tonigan, J. S., & Carroll, K. (2019). A meta-analysis of cognitive-behavioral therapy for alcohol or other drug use disorders: Treatment efficacy by contrast condition. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, 87*(12), 1093–1105.
- McGuire, J. (2021). *Cost-effectiveness analysis: StrongMinds*. HLI.
<https://www.happierlivesinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/StrongMinds-CEA.pdf>
- Mears, D. P., & Bhati, A. S. (2006). No community is an island: The effects of resource deprivation on urban violence in spatially and socially proximate communities. *Criminology; an Interdisciplinary Journal, 44*(3), 509–548.
- Mercy, J. A., Hillis, S. D., Butchart, A., Bellis, M. A., Ward, C. L., Fang, X., & Rosenberg, M. L. (2017). Interpersonal violence: Global impact and paths to prevention. In *Disease Control Priorities, Third Edition (Volume 7): Injury Prevention and Environmental Health* (pp. 71–96). The World Bank.
- Murray, J., Cerqueira, D. R. de C., & Kahn, T. (2013). Crime and violence in Brazil: Systematic review of time trends, prevalence rates and risk factors. *Aggression and Violent Behavior, 18*(5), 471–483.
- Oppenheimer, A. (2023, May 12). *Rising crime rates are pushing Latin America's political pendulum to the right*. Yahoo Movies.
<https://ca.news.yahoo.com/rising-crime-rates-pushing-latin-231706211.html>
- Rozo, S. (2014). Is murder bad for business and real income? The effects of violent crime on economic activity. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2481440>
- Saddiq, S. A., & Abu Bakar, A. S. (2019). Impact of economic and financial crimes on economic growth in emerging and developing countries: A systematic review. *Journal of Financial Crime, 26*(3), 910–920.

- Shinohara, K., Honyashiki, M., Imai, H., Hunot, V., Caldwell, D. M., Davies, P., Moore, T. H. M., Furukawa, T. A., & Churchill, R. (2013). Behavioural therapies versus other psychological therapies for depression. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 2013(10), CD008696.
- Stickley, A., Koyanagi, A., Roberts, B., Goryakin, Y., & McKee, M. (2015). Crime and subjective well-being in the countries of the former Soviet Union. *BMC Public Health*, 15(1), 1010.
- UNODC. (2013). *Global Study on Homicide 2013*.
https://www.unodc.org/documents/gsh/pdfs/2014_GLOBAL_HOMICIDE_BOOK_web.pdf
- Uphoff, E., Ekers, D., Robertson, L., Dawson, S., Sanger, E., South, E., Samaan, Z., Richards, D., Meader, N., & Churchill, R. (2020). Behavioural activation therapy for depression in adults. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 7(7), CD013305.
- Vida Plena. (2024). *2023 Vida Plena Impact Report*. Vida Plena.
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_6p0dt2blcNphEDHAVuz1YiiAk5LLWob/view?usp=drive_link&usp=embed_facebook
- Walter, R. J., Acolin, A., & Tillyer, M. S. (2024). Association between property investments and crime on commercial and residential streets: Implications for maximizing public safety benefits. *SSM - Population Health*, 25(101537), 101537.
- WHO. (2023, October 11). *Youth violence*.
<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/youth-violence>
- World Bank. (2018, May 17). *Stopping Crime and Violence in Latin America: A Look at Prevention from Cradle to Adulthood*. World Bank; World Bank Group.
<https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2018/05/17/fin-a-la-violencia-en-america-latina-una-mirada-a-la-prevencion-desde-la-infancia-hasta-la-edad-adulta>